

LIFE SATISFACTION AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF ADOLESCENT BOYS AND GIRLS IN KASHMIR

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ABSTRACT

The present study was conducted to compare the life satisfaction and academic achievement of adolescent boys and girls. The sample for the present study consisted of 400 students in which 200 were adolescent boys and 200 were adolescent girls. The investigators used Diener, E., Emmons, R.A., Larsen, R.J., and Griffin, S. Life satisfaction scale to assess the life satisfaction of sample subjects. The previous two years academic achievement served as academic indicator of the sample subjects. The investigator used various statistical techniques viz, mean, S.D., t-test to analyze the data. The statistical data revealed that there is significant difference between adolescent boys and girls on life satisfaction and academic achievement. Adolescent girls were found to have better life satisfaction than adolescent boys and it was also found that adolescent girls were found on higher side on their academic achievement than the adolescent boys.

Keywords: life satisfaction, academic achievement, adolescent, boys, girls.

INTRODUCTION

Life satisfaction concept has for long been a subject of philosophical speculations. The study of satisfaction with life (SWL) has developed within the area of hedonic psychology (Kahneman, Diener, & Schwarz, 1999). Life satisfaction is often considered a desirable goal, in and of itself, stemming from the Aristotelian ethical model, eudaimonism, (from *eudaimonia*, the Greek word for happiness) where correct actions lead to individual well-being, with happiness representing the supreme good (Myers, 1992). As a psychological construct, life satisfaction is considered a cognitive process arising from an individual's assessment of his or her own life according to criteria generated internally (Diener, Emmons, Larsen & Griffin, 1985). Further, satisfaction with life has been conceptualized as a component of subjective well-being (Diener, Suh, Lucas, & Smith, 1999). They have identified four components of subjective well-being: pleasant affect, unpleasant affect, life satisfaction and domain satisfaction (see fig.1).

The concept of life satisfaction is conceived *as the degree to which an individual judges the overall quality of his/her life as a whole favorably* (Veenhoven, 1991); the term is thus used synonymously with happiness (Veenhoven, 1991) and subjective well-being (Diener, 1994). Life satisfaction can also be defined as the cognitive component of subjective well-being (Campbell, Converse & Rodgers 1976; Diener 1994). Kaalish (1975) defined life satisfaction as *accepting your life meaningfully, feeling that at least you have achieved the important goal, harmonizing with your surroundings effectively and satisfying your drives without having emotional and social problems*. Nowadays, life satisfaction and happiness have become the main interest of studies in different fields of psychology (i.e. clinical psychology, cross-cultural psychology, social psychology, and industrial psychology) and have been transformed into what is known today as the field of *positive psychology* (Strack et al., 1991).

Diener (1984) stated that "The hallmark of satisfaction with life is that it centres on personal judgments, not upon some criteria that is judged to be important by the researchers". Diener (1994) noted that the more global

construct of subjective well-being is a multidimensional construct, composed of cognitive appraisals (life satisfaction) and affective components. Diener, Suh, Oishi, Lucas, and Smith (1999) suggested that the most commonly accepted model of subjective well-being conceptualizes it as having an emotional component (e.g., sadness, anxiety, and joy) and a cognitive component (satisfaction with life). Although much of the quality of life literature fails to distinguish between subjective well-being and satisfaction with life, it should be noted that the constructs are not equivalent. Subjective well-being is a more broadly defined construct having both cognitive and affective components. Life satisfaction, on the other hand, is limited to the cognitive component of subjective well-being and thus tends to be more stable. Satisfaction with life is the criterion variable (dependent measure/variable) in the present study.

Academic achievement is a capacity to excel others which is important component for every person especially for a student to be successful, as he/she is always facing competitive situation in his educational career. Achievement after all is the end product of all educational endeavors. The main concern of all educational efforts is to see that the learners achieves. A teacher is supported to arrange the educational situation in a way so as to encourage pupils to put their heart and soul in the school activities. Hence the problem of achievement has drawn sufficient attention of researchers in the field of educational psychology.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The following objectives were formulated for the present investigation.

1. To study the life satisfaction of adolescent boys and girls.
2. To study the Academic Achievement of adolescent boys and girls
3. To compare of adolescent boys and girls on Life Satisfaction.
4. To compare of adolescent boys and girls on Academic Achievement.

NULL HYPOTHESES

The following hypotheses were formulated for the present investigation.

1. There is no significant difference between adolescent boys and girls on Life Satisfaction.
2. There is no significant difference between adolescent boys and girls on Academic Achievement.

OPERATIONAL DEFINATIONS OF TERMS AND VARIABLES

1. **Satisfaction with Life Scale-** For the purpose of this study satisfaction with life is defined as a general appraisal of an individual's quality of life according to his/her personal standards. Individuals who obtain a score of 31-35 on SWLS are highly satisfied, while as 26-30 are satisfied, 21-25 - slightly satisfied, 15-19- slightly dissatisfied, 10-14-dissatisfied, 5-9, -extremely dissatisfied The composite score of the SWLS is 35.
2. **Academic Achievement:** Academic achievement of Boys and Girls secondary students refers to the knowledge attained and skills developed in the school subjects. So, academic achievement means the achievement of students in academic subjects. For this purpose, the aggregate Marks obtained by the subjects in previous two exams served as measures of academic achievement.

SAMPLE: The sample for the present study consisted of 400 adolescents (200 boys and 200 girls) selected randomly from the different schools in Kashmir.

The breakup of the sample are as under:

Group	N	Total
Adolescent Boys	200	400
Adolescent Girls	200	

Tools Used

The data for the present study was collected with the help of the Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS) by Diener, E., Emmons, R.A., Larsen, R.J., and Griffin, S. (1985).

Aggregate percentage of marks of pervious two classes, as indicator of Academic Achievement.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table 1 : Comparison of Adolescent Boys and Girls on Life Satisfaction

Range	Respondents		Remarks
	Boys	Girls	
26 – 30	9 (18%)	11 (22%)	Satisfied
21 – 25	10 (20%)	14 (28%)	Slightly satisfied
20-24	6 (12%)	12 (24%)	Neutral
15 - 19	6 (12%)	7 (14%)	Slightly dissatisfied
10 – 14	6 (12%)	8 (16%)	Dissatisfied
5 - 9	5 (10%)	6 (12%)	Extremely dissatisfied
Total	50	50	

The above table reveals that the highest percentages of adolescent girls (24%) are slightly satisfied, while highest percentage (20%) of adolescent boys are slightly satisfied. In case of adolescent boys 18% are satisfied, 12% are neutral, 12% are slightly dissatisfied and 10% are extremely satisfied. While, in case of adolescent girls 22% are satisfied, 24% are neutral, 14% are slightly dissatisfied, 16% are dissatisfied and only 12% are extremely dissatisfied.

Table 2: Showing the mean comparison of Boys and Girls on Life Satisfaction (N= 50 in each group)

Group	N	Mean	S.D	t- value	Level of Significance
Boys	50	21.7	4.19	2.29	Significant at 0.05 Level
Girls	50	23.42	3.35		

The above table shows the mean comparison of boys and girls on life satisfaction. The calculated t-value (2.29) is greater than the tabulated t-value at 0.05 level of significance, which depicts that there is significant difference between adolescent boys and girls on life satisfaction. The above result clarifies that adolescent girls have better life satisfaction than adolescent boys.

In the light of above discussion, the hypotheses No. 1 which reads as “There is no significant difference between adolescent boys and girls on Life Satisfaction” stands rejected.

Table 3: Mean comparison of Adolescent Boys and Girls on Academic Achievement (N=50 in each group).

Group	Mean	S.D.	t- value	Level of significance
Boys	13.69	2.59	3.15	Significant at 0.01 Level
Girls	15.68	4.05		

The above table shows the significant difference between adolescent boys and girls on academic achievement, the difference was found significant at 0.01 level. It further indicates that adolescent girls were found on higher side on their academic achievement than the adolescent boys.

In light of the above discussion, the hypotheses No.2 which reads as, “There is no significant difference between adolescent boys and girls on academic achievement” stands rejected.

CONCLUSIONS

The following are some of the conclusions drawn from the present study.

1. It has been found that the highest percentages of adolescent girls (24%) are slightly satisfied, while highest percentage (20%) of adolescent boys are slightly satisfied. In case of adolescent boys 18% are satisfied, 12% are neutral, 12% are slightly dissatisfied and 10% are extremely satisfied. While, in case of adolescent girls 22% are satisfied, 24% are neutral, 14% are slightly dissatisfied, 16% are dissatisfied and only 12% are extremely dissatisfied.
2. It has been found that adolescent boys and girls differ significant on Life Satisfaction. Adolescent girls were found to have better life satisfaction than adolescent boys.
3. It has been found that there is a significant difference between adolescent boys and girls on academic achievement. Adolescent girls were found to have better academic achievement than adolescent boys.

REFERENCES

2. Arrindell, W. A., Meeuwesen, L., & Huyse, F. J. (1991). The satisfaction with life scale (SWLS): Psychometric properties in a non-psychiatric medical outpatient sample. *Personality and Individual Differences, 12*, 117-123.
3. Best, J. W. (1989). *Research in education*. 9th Edition.
4. Chandra, R. and Koul, K. (2006). Comparative analysis of visually impaired and orthopedically handicapped children on academic performance, level of education, level of aspiration in northern Assam. *3rd Survey of Research in Education, NCERT, New Delhi*.
5. Costa, P. T. & McCrae, R. R. (1984). Personality as a lifelong determinant of well-being, in C, Malatesta and C. Izard (eds.). *Affective Processes in Adult Development and Aging*. Beverley Hills, Sage.
6. Daly, M. & Rose, R. (2007). *First European quality of life survey: Key findings from a policy perspective*. Luxembourg: Office for Official Publications of the European Communities.

7. Delhey, J. (2004). *Life satisfaction in an enlarged Europe*. Luxembourg: Office for Official Publications of the European Communities.
8. Diener, E., & Diener, M. (1995). Cross-cultural correlates of life satisfaction and self-esteem. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 68, 653–663.
9. Diener, E., Emmons, R. A., Larsen, R. J. & Griffin, S. (1985). The Satisfaction With Life Scale. *Journal of Personality Assessment*, 49, 71-75.
10. Evans, M. D. R., & Kelley, J. (2004). Effect of family structure on life satisfaction: Australian evidence? *Social Indicators Research*, 69, 303-349.
11. Greenspan, S. I. (1989). Emotional Intelligence. In K.Field, B.J.Cohler, & G. Wool (Eds.). *Learning and Education: Psychoanalytic Perspectives*. Madison, CT. International Universities Press.
12. Harikrishan, M (1992). A study of academic achievement of the students of higher secondary stage in relation to achievement, motivation and socio-economic status. M.Phil education, Anamalai University. Vol. 2nd, Fifth Survey. Pp 1878.
13. Haybron. D. M. (2005). *Life Satisfaction, Ethical Reflection, and the Science of Happiness*. Department of Philosophy, Saint Louis University. Retrieved from <http://pages.slu.edu/faculty/haybrond/LS%20Ethical%20reflection%20&%20science%20of%20H%20v4single.pdf>
14. Heller, D., Watson, D., & Hies, R. (2004). The role of person versus situation in life satisfaction: a critical examination. *Psychological Bulletin*, 130(4), 574-600.
15. Helliwell, J. (2001). How's life? Combining individual and national variables to explain subjective well-being. Paper presented at the *Annual Meeting of Queen's International Institute on Social Policy*. Kingston, CA-ON.
16. Huebner, E. S. (1991b). Further validation of the Students' Life Satisfaction Scale: The independence of satisfaction and affect ratings. *Journal of Psycho- educational Assessment*, 9, 363–368.
17. Huebner, E. S. (1991c). Initial development of the Students' Life Satisfaction Scale. *School Psychology International*, 12, 231–240.
18. Jackson, D. N. (1974). *Personality research form manual*. Port Huron: Research Psychologists Press. Rev. Ed.
19. Kerlinger (1973). Foundations of behavioural research, 14
Kerlinger, P. N. New Delhi. *Sarjeet Publications*.
20. Leung, J., & Leung, K. (1992). Life Satisfaction, self-concept and relationship with parents in adolescence. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*. 21 (6), 653-665. doi: 10.1007/BF01538737.
21. Liang, J. (1985). A structural integration of the Affect Balance Scale and the Life Satisfaction Index A. *Journal of Gerontology*, 40(5), 552-561.

22. Madhu and Greval (1990). Relationship between study habits and academic achievement of undergraduate home science final year students. *Indian Educational Review*. 25(3): 71-74.
23. Madhuri (1988). A study of factors in pupil academic achievement in different streams of courses of the higher secondary stage. *Vol. 1st, Fifth Survey*.
24. Misra, M. (1986). A critical study of the socio-economic status on academic achievement of higher secondary schools in rural and urban areas of Kanpur. *Ph.D. Education*.
25. Ojwala (1990). Pupils academic achievement in relationship to their intelligence, neuroticism and locus of control. M.Phil Education, Anamalai University. *Vol. 2nd, Fifth Survey*. Pp 1896.
26. Rigby, B. T., & Huebner, E. S. (2005). Do causal attributions mediate the relationship between personality characteristics and life satisfaction in adolescence? *Psychology in the Schools*, 42, 91–99.
27. Royce Sadler, D. (2009). Grade integrity and the representation of academic achievement. *Studies in Higher Education*. 34(7): 807-826.
28. Samal (1990). Relationship between planning and academic achievement of boys and girls: Effect of home environment variables. *Vol. 2nd, Fifth Survey*. Pp 1911.
29. Schimmack, U., Diener, E., & Oishi, S. (2002). Life satisfaction is a Momentary Judgment and a Stable Personality Characteristic: The Use of Chronically Accessible and Stable Sources. *Journal of Personality*, 70, 345-385.